

IMPROVING POLICY TO SUPPORT WIDER UPTAKE OF MARINE LITTER CLEAN-UP TECHNOLOGIES ACROSS EUROPEAN SEAS: THE CLAIM CONTRIBUTION

SUMMARY

Marine litter pollution, including plastic litter, is a major environmental challenge with significant marine ecosystem impacts and socio-economic costs on sectors including tourism and recreation, aquaculture, fisheries and commercial shipping. Many national laws, policies, initiatives and funds address marine litter, but they are often part of broader regulatory frameworks and without a direct link to best available technologies to prevent litter from entering the sea, or clean it up once it has reached the sea.

The distinction between macro and micro plastic litter is crucial in this context, since they require different technological and governance solutions, including for their clean-up. Whilst the best way to tackle plastic marine litter is to prevent it from reaching the sea at all, unless and until full prevention is achieved, appropriate technologies and policies are still needed to enable litter clean-up.

Existing policies provide an important regulatory framework for assessing the extent of the marine litter problem in general. For example, marine litter is included as an indicator that must be monitored under the EU's Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD). However, the link to concrete actions addressing different types of litter from different sources is often lacking. Exceptions include the marine litter action plans developed under the Regional Sea Conventions, which have an important role in implementing the MSFD, or the 2019 Port Reception Facilities Directive (PRFD). Nevertheless, additional policies and incentives are still needed to tackle the plastic pollution problem.

To encourage the wider use of best available marine litter clean-up technologies, we recommend that:

- (1) existing laws and policy approaches are adapted to provide coherent legal mandates for the actual clean-up of different types of marine litter, including an explicit reference to marine litter in relevant legislation;
- (2) new policy targets are set to limit macro and micro plastics in fresh and marine waters, and existing and new targets monitored to ensure they are met;
- (3) funding and financial incentives, and economic instruments, are mobilised to support the wider use of proven cost-effective clean-up technologies;
- (4) coordination and clear allocation of responsibilities is ensured between different levels of government and other responsible entities;
- (5) platforms are created for more systematic, active engagement of key public and private sector stakeholders, to inform policy development, implementation and revision in support of the best use of advanced technical and technological knowledge.

KEYWORDS

Marine litter; plastic pollution; clean-up technology; policy drivers; policy barriers; Baltic Sea; Mediterranean Sea

RELEVANCE TO LEGISLATION

- 🏊 Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) (2008/56/EC)
- 🏊 Waste Framework Directive (2008/98/EC)
- 🏊 European Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy (COM/2018/028)
- 🏊 Port Reception Facilities (PRF) Directive (2019/883/EU)
- 🏊 Urban Wastewater Treatment (UWWT) Directive (91/271/EEC) and its ongoing revision
- 🏊 Water Framework Directive (2000/60/EC)
- 🏊 Marine Equipment Directive (2014/90/EU)
- 🏊 Directive on the reduction of the impact of certain plastic products on the environment (Single Use Plastics (SUP) Directive 2019/904/EU)
- 🏊 HELCOM's Regional Action Plan for Marine Litter in the Baltic Sea
- 🏊 OSPAR's Regional Action Plan for Prevention and Management of Marine Litter in the North-East Atlantic
- 🏊 UNEP/MAP's Regional Plan on Marine Litter Management in the Mediterranean
- 🏊 Basel Convention's Plastic Waste Amendments
- 🏊 MARPOL Convention's Annex V

RELEVANCE TO ACTUAL ENVIRONMENTAL PROBLEMS

Marine plastic litter, plastic pollution, waste management, water quality, coastal management

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DESCRIPTION OF THE PROBLEM

Marine litter pollution, including plastic litter, is a complex issue that has become one of the major environmental challenges of our time. The main sources are a wide range of human activities including industry, urban waste, tourism, maritime traffic, fishing, cosmetics and even laundry. Marine litter ends up in the sea mainly from rivers and torrents as well as from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs). Natural environmental factors such as ocean currents, waves and weather also impact on how litter is spread, transported, sinks and accumulates in the seas and oceans.

Plastic litter in the ocean has **significant impacts on the marine environment, the marine life within it, and the benefits that humans derive from it** (such as food, leisure and transport). For example, it has been estimated that by 2050, 99% of seabirds are likely to have ingested plastic (Wilcox et al. 2015). Plastic litter has substantial social-economic costs in various economic sectors, including tourism and recreation, aquaculture, fisheries and commercial shipping (Mouat et al., 2010; Brouwer et al., 2017). The economic cost of the impact of plastic litter on the marine environment (and the benefits derived from the marine environment) has been estimated at between US\$3,300 and US\$33,000 per tonne per year (Beaumont et al., 2019).

Larger items of plastic litter – macro plastics¹ – are readily visible on the ocean’s surface and along coasts and beaches, but smaller micro plastics² are also a major issue. Micro plastics may come from the break-up of larger pieces of plastic, from larger plastic particles fragmenting, and from a variety of substances including cosmetics, synthetic clothing or even car tyre wear (McCormick et al., 2014; Napper et al., 2015). These microplastics build up in oceans, seabeds and beaches all over the world (Moore, 2008) as well as in marine organisms from plankton to mammals (Wright et al., 2013). This can pose a long-term risk for marine food chains (Betts, 2008) as the ingested microplastics, and chemicals contained within them, are passed up the food chain, including to humans (Beaumont et al., 2019).

The best way to tackle plastic marine litter is to prevent it from reaching the sea at all. Monitoring efforts – both technological and policy-driven – can play an important role in prevention, by identifying where plastic litter comes from and the hot spots where it ends up. However, unless and until full prevention is achieved, **appropriate technologies and policies are still needed to enable the clean-up of litter** that has reached fresh and marine waters. This includes methods for capture and remove litter from the aquatic environment, as well as technologies to support the re-use of collected litter, for example by using it to generate energy.

Numerous laws, policies, initiatives and funds already exist that are relevant for addressing marine litter. Recognising that it is a transnational issue, there are several **international efforts** in place including Annex V of the International Convention for the Prevention of Pollution from Ships (MARPOL), which bans ships from dumping litter at sea, the Basel Convention’s Plastic Waste Amendment, the Global Partnership on Marine Litter (GPML), the UNEP Honolulu strategy and CleanSeas campaign, and the G7 Action Plan to Combat Marine Litter.

There is also a significant level of **regional cooperation**. In the EU, the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) forms a broader framework for more effective protection of the marine environment across Europe, and includes marine litter as one of the indicators for good environmental status (GES) that must be monitored. The HELCOM Commission’s and OSPAR Commission’s Regional Action Plans on Marine Litter and the Regional Plan on Marine Litter Management in the Mediterranean have an important role in the MSFD’s implementation. In addition, the EU Port Reception Facilities (PRF) Directive aims to reduce the discharge of ship-generated waste and cargo residues at sea by requiring that ports provide facilities to collect these types of waste.

Many **national laws, policies and initiatives** are relevant to marine litter and the use of associated technologies, including national marine strategies, waste legislation, waste management plans, legislation on specific types of plastic waste such as packaging, plastic bags or microbeads, water and waste water legislation, and general environmental strategies. There are also some **funds**, including from national, EU or regional Convention sources, that could provide financing for marine litter clean-up projects, but additional incentives are still needed to tackle the plastic pollution problem.

Although policy frameworks are in place, some policies do not currently explicitly refer to marine litter (e.g. the Water Framework Directive and the Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive). Others refer to marine litter only in general terms, with no clear distinction between macro and micro plastics (e.g. the MSFD and Waste Framework Directive). On the other hand, the EU Plastics Strategy and the Single-Use Plastics Directive both clearly highlight the problem of plastic marine litter as a key reason for their existence. **Most policies also do not provide a direct link to best available technologies** to prevent litter from entering the sea at the main source points, i.e. WWTPs and river estuaries. The **lack of distinction in policies between macro and micro plastics** is problematic in this regard, since these different types of litter require different technological and governance solutions for both their prevention and clean-up. In addition, there is **no systematic, common approach to monitoring** micro plastic litter in particular. Taken together, these factors mean that the **direct link to the marine litter issue in legal, policy and funding frameworks, and the data to back up action, is often missing**.

There are various **technologies available for the clean-up of marine litter**. For example, the CLAIM project is developing innovative technologies to: capture microplastics from wastewater by treating plastic particles with photocatalysis and nanocoating; prevent riverine litter from reaching marine environments; and create energy from collected litter using pyrolysis (see box on next page). However, this alone is not enough. Legal and policy frameworks (and where appropriate, financial incentives and support) need to facilitate the use of those technologies, or at the very least not pose a barrier to their use. At the same time policies should ban the disposal of plastics in landfills.

1 Macro plastics are plastic pieces larger than 5 mm that are visible to the naked eye.

2 Micro plastics are plastic pieces smaller than 5 mm that are not visible to the human eye.

CLAIM'S TECHNOLOGICAL SOLUTIONS FOR LITTER COLLECTED FROM RIVERS AND THE SEA

The **CLEAN** (CLAIM's Litter Entrapping Autonomous Network) **TRASH** (Tactical Recovery Accumulation System Hellas) system collects macro plastics (>5 mm) and other floating litter from the surface of water systems, such as river estuaries and storm drains, before it can enter the marine environment, without impeding the movement of animals or vessels. Designed, developed and constructed by New Naval (Greece), the system has already been successfully demonstrated in 2019 at the Kifissos River estuary in Greece. After heavy rainfall, within 10 days the system collected 8 cubic metres (1,175 kg) of waste, mostly plastic. The system can function with a cost of less than 0.00024 € per cubic metre of water filtered through it.

The litter collected by the CLEAN TRASH system can feed CLAIM's two innovative small-scale **pyrolizer systems**, developed by IRIS (Italy):

- **PYRI**, a thermal plasma assisted-pyrolizer for use in ports, able to treat 70 kg of marine litter per hour.
- **PYR2**, an induction assisted-pyrolizer for use on board vessels, with a pre-treatment system, able to treat 30 kg of marine litter per hour.

CLAIM's pyrolizers generate a high temperature to transform solid waste, including plastic, into combustible syngas. The gas can be used immediately on-site as an energy source in ports, marinas or on board vessels. The syngas produced is around 57% higher in calorific value³ than the biomass gasifiers currently on the market, and each kg of plastic can create around 2.5 Nm³ of syngas. The electrical balance (electrical energy produced potentially minus electrical energy consumed) is positive in both devices, even when there is a small quantity of litter. The net electric revenue is estimated at about 22,000 € per year. PYR2's induction technology has been demonstrated to be more promising than PYRI's plasma technology in terms of dimensions, electrical consumption and reduced maintenance.

The technologies can be optimized by increasing the quantity of treated marine litter to 30–70 kg per hour, and using assisted-pyrolysis induction technology combined with catalysts for the treatment of syngas. This achieves a significant increase in generated electricity and a clear reduction in operating costs, making the device commercially viable in both technical and economic terms.

CLAIM's technological solutions for microplastic removal from Waste Water Treatment Plants (WWTPs)

CLAIM has developed an **automated filtering system** to prevent and manage micro plastics (< 5 mm) discharges from WWTPs. The system consists of two filters (one sand filter and one multilayer filter with sand and an active carbon layer), which together can remove 95.67% of micro plastics at the scale up to 50 µm.

The retained microplastics are then fed into a **photocatalytic device** that uses green nanotechnology-based coatings which, when activated by sunlight, encourage polymer degradation without releasing the nanoparticles into the water stream. Around one week of visible light irradiation is needed to reduce the model plastic particles (PVC) of 73 µm to 28 µm (a 96.5% reduction in particle volume). With two weeks' irradiation, particle size was reduced to 0.4 µm (an estimated 99.9% reduction in particle volume).

There is still a lack of information to assess the risks of nanoplastics in the context of global plastic pollution, but until this knowledge gap is addressed, the CLAIM technology provides a suitable method for mitigating nanoplastic hazards.

³ Calorific value of 2.05 kWh/Nm³ compared with 1.3 kWh/Nm³ (Nm³ is 'normal cubic metres').

RECOMMENDATIONS

To ensure that laws and policies better support the wider take-up of cost-effective marine litter clean-up technologies, the following **recommendations are made for consideration by policy-makers**:

🌊 **Adapt existing international, regional and national laws and policies** to provide coherent legal mandates for the actual clean-up of different types of marine litter.

Explicit reference to micro and macro plastic marine litter should be added to relevant legislation beyond the Single-Use Plastics Directive. Ideally an explicit definition of micro and macro plastic litter should be added, including in the MSFD. A simpler alternative approach would be to insert a clear reference to the EU Plastics Strategy and/or SUP Directive when each piece of legislation is next revised. This would also create greater coherence between legislative acts with respect to their relevance to tackling marine litter. This would help to demonstrate the importance of the issue, providing inspiration to polluters not to pollute, inspiration to technology developers to innovate, and inspiration to potential investors to offer financial support.

🌊 **Introduce new policy targets and ensure both existing and new marine litter-related targets are monitored and met.** Existing targets and associated guidance can be further specified, and new targets set, for example to **limit the amount of macro and microplastics in fresh and marine waters**. This would better implement the waste prevention and “polluter pays” principles. In parallel with the targets, improved monitoring would both create a drive for action and provide a better baseline of information against which to demonstrate the benefits of clean-up technologies.

🌊 **Develop a specific piece of EU legislation to tackle microplastic pollution.** There is a dedicated Directive on single-use plastics, but it does not explicitly cover microplastics. The creation of a complementary “microplastics directive” would help to clarify the EU’s objectives on the issue and provide a useful distinction between macro and micro plastic pollution, thereby encouraging technological and governance solutions appropriate to both. It could for example include targets to limit microplastics in the environment, provide guidance on how to monitor the presence of microplastics in the environment, place restrictions on microplastics’ use in products, and introduce producer responsibility for products likely to emit or degrade into microplastics. The SUP Directive could provide inspiration for the new legislation.

🌊 The ongoing (2021) review of the **UWWT Directive** offers a more immediate opportunity to promote action on microplastics. Consideration should be given to: setting limits for the amount of microplastics present in treated waste water and sludge (to be defined through appropriate research); obliging additional treatment steps to remove microplastics (perhaps only in larger plants); adding requirements for WWTPs to better monitor microplastics (with accompanying guidance); and/or obliging producers to financially support these actions (for example through producer responsibility).

🌊 **Mobilise funding and/or financial incentives** explicitly to support the wider use of proven clean-up technologies, especially on public infrastructure such as river estuaries and storm drains as well as WWTPs.

Options include providing **financial support for research** into, and deployment of, technologies, and offering **grants, subsidies or loans to SMEs, start-ups and early adopters** of technologies. At the EU level, potential funding vehicles include **Horizon Europe**, the **Cohesion Fund**, **LIFE**, and the **European Maritime and Fisheries Fund**, as well as the **EIB’s Clean Oceans Initiative**. Consideration could be given to ring-fencing a proportion of these funds to marine litter action, tracking the amount of funding allocated to this area, and stepping up efforts ensure uptake of the funds for this purpose (for example, the Clean Oceans Initiative aims to provide €2 billion to public and private sector clean ocean projects by 2023).

In addition, encouraging the wider use of **economic instruments such as extended producer responsibility (EPR) or product taxes** could help to raise finances to be used for this purpose.

 Ensure coordination and clear allocation of responsibilities between different levels of government (EU, national, regional, local) **and other responsible entities** such as water companies and waste management companies. This would help to clearly define responsibilities, ensuring that the issue of tackling marine litter doesn't fall through the cracks.

 Create platforms for stakeholder engagement and best practice sharing to inform policy relevant to marine litter. This could take the form of online forums or expert advisory groups to the EU institutions, comprising businesses, citizens' organisations, volunteer groups, NGOs and the research and scientific community. All of these stakeholders can provide highly relevant insights for policy development, implementation and revision, including evidence demonstrating the need for technology and the benefits of specific technologies, how to adapt legislation to support the best use of advanced technical and technological knowledge, proposals for marine litter monitoring methods, and ideas on how to gather public support for policies. More systematic, active engagement of key public and private sector stakeholders by policy-makers would help create ever more robust marine litter policies. In addition, it would allow for the sharing of knowledge and best practices on technologies' implementation to ensure their effective use across regional seas in support of implementing EU legislation.

Based on the report "Report of legal and policy framework, including results from stakeholder interviews" by Emma Watkins (IEEP), Sofia Frantzi (VUA), Roy Brouwer (VUA), Pieter van Beukering (VUA), Maria Cunha (UC), Hanna Dijkstra (VUA), Sem Duijndam (VUA), Charles Okoli (CAU), Mia Pantzar (IEEP), Ignacio Rada Cotera (IKERC), Katrin Rehdanz (CAU), Karsten Seidel (IKERC), George Triantaphyllidis (HCMR), Hela Jaziri (INSTM). Deliverable 5.2 under the CLAIM project (Cleaning Litter by developing and Applying Innovative Methods in European seas)

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